

ISic0628

Epitaph of Abdalas

Language

Latin

Type

funerary

Material

marble

Object

tablet

Editor

Jonathan Prag

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Jonathan Prag

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Capitonia

Place of origin (modern)

Ramacca

Provenance

Contrada Ventrelli, nr. Ramacca

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Ramacca, Museo Civico
Archeologico di Ramacca

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height 26.5 cm

Width 35 cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line

1
: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to

2
: mm

Text

1. D(is) M(anibus) s(acrum)
2. Abdalas Domi
3. tiae Domitiani
4. magister magnus
5. ovium qui bene vix(it)
6. in officio ann(os) LXXX

Apparatus

Translation (en)

Sacred to the spirits of the dead; Abdalas, (slave of) Domitia (wife of) Domitian,
great master of

the sheep, who lived well in his job; eighty years old

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 175711

EDR 079873

EDCS 8300354

Bibliography

1888-. L'année épigraphique: revue des publications épigraphiques relatives a l'antiquité romaine.. *L'année épigraphique : revue des publications épigraphiques relatives a l'antiquité romaine..* At 1985.0483

Wilson, R.J.A. 1990. Sicily under the Roman Empire: the archaeology of a Roman province, 36 B.C. - A.D. 535. Warminster. At 215 n.102
fig.175

Salmeri, G. 1984. Un magister ovium di Domizia Longina in Sicilia. *ASNP*. 3.14: 13-23.

Manganaro, G. 1988. La Sicilia da Sesto Pompeo a Diocleziano. *ANRW*. 2.11.1: 3-89. At 17 n.62

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